

***After COP26 Towards High Values. We don't Need To Change The World.
Lawyers Step In. 10 Years after Lautsi v. Italy.***
Olga Nickole Kuyan

Abstract

The message from the Dasgupta Review on the Economics of Biodiversity is recent, loud and clear: we must fix our relationship with the natural world or destroy human prosperity, well-being and our future. The COP 26 UN Climate Change Conference, hosted by the UK in partnership with Italy, was taking place from 31 October to 12 November 2021 in the Scottish Event Campus (SEC) in Glasgow, UK. Lawyers step in. There's lots of dimensions to start this sort of discussion, and lawyers are as good as any: everything in the universe has both particle and wave nature, at the same time. All is waves, everything in the universe has wave nature. Of course, everything in the universe also has particle nature. Lawyers call for the progress of implementation of the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs). Lawyers call for the collaboration to evidence a growing momentum around climate action, to win in resolving the rules around carbon markets etc and to assuage vulnerable countries' concerns about long-promised climate financing from rich nations etc, in total to change the reality. Lawyers call on to attend to our own personal development, to raise our level of consciousness. Lawyers forward the Golden Hours Idea, discussing the consequences of Lautsi v. Italy case and its importance for the current world situation.

Keywords: the Economics of Biodiversity, Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, COP26, crisis, judge, lawyer, politician, mystic, Know thyself, change, development, complexity, Thinking Hat, golden hour, meditation, physical training, Lautsi case, Christianity, Mediterranean Lifestyle, mimetic theory, Integral ecology

Receive the Natural response. The origin of the COVID-19 pandemic is undoubtedly due to the devastation and destruction of the planet. From the industrial revolution¹ onwards, we, homo sapiens sapiens,² have devastated more than 2/3 of the earth's surface for industrialization, urbanization, and agricultural production processes. Not only that, we have deforested the equivalent of the surface of the African continent for the intensive breeding of cattle and the production of red meat. All this has dramatically expanded social and environmental inequalities and injustices.

The message from the Dasgupta Review on the Economics of Biodiversity³ is recent, loud and clear: we must fix our relationship with the natural world or destroy human prosperity, well-being and our future. Manuela Monti and Carlo Alberto Redi, two scholars from the University of Pavia, Italy, summarize⁴ some of the themes of that fascinating and disturbing message as follows: "The planet Earth is at its end. We have come to the time when man-made artifacts and products (buildings, plastics, and so on) that amount to about 1.1 teratonnes (a weight, equivalent to about 1,100 billion tons) have surpassed the biomass of living beings (less than a teratonne, plants and animals). The demands on resources (raw materials, fuels, timber, food, etc.) and services (oxygen production, absorption of atmospheric carbon dioxide, recycling of nutrients, ability to eliminate waste, and so on) that we place on the Earth today are such that we should to have almost two planets (1.6 to be precise) to satisfy them..."⁵.

We fully share. We have reached an extreme point in the ruin of our planet which reacts, gives us a natural answer, its answer. And many manifestations of this response, we are

1 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Industrial_Revolution

2 <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Homo-sapiens-sapiens>

3 <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/final-report-the-economics-of-biodiversity-the-dasgupta-review>

4 [file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/15620-Articolo-49497-1-10-20211018%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/15620-Articolo-49497-1-10-20211018%20(1).pdf)

5 Corriere della Sera - la Lettura (February 28, 2021), 5.

witnessing, are irreversible and will never change. Human economic welfare and the natural resources on which it depends appear to be hopelessly antithetical, a battle which Nature will inevitably lose.

The only answer is: we need an enemy to grow, we need obstacles to evolve, to challenge ourselves and bring out the best in ourselves. Is it enough as an answer? People do not know. What do you think? Etty Hillesum⁶ provokes us: "That is your disease; you want to capture life in formulas of your own. You want to embrace all aspects of life with your intellect instead of allowing... .. yourself to be embraced by life. You want to create the world all over again each time, instead of enjoying it as it is. There is something compulsive about it all".⁷

Gabor Maté⁸says: "Materialistic Society creates Toxic Culture".⁹ Z.Bauman¹⁰concludes that the current reality is characterized by individuals who do not have time nor space to relate with the everlasting, with absolute and established values.¹¹

People lack broad horizons, the profound vision of becoming, people restrict themselves to their small spaces of fruitless and miserable selfishness. Lofty ideals fade, goals are becoming more and more isolated and if they can be called great, then not by their content, but by the amount of means necessary to achieve them. Men act for things of little value, wealth, power, self-affirmation, status symbol, the pleasure that ends the next day. People prefer the Society of the Spectacle.¹²

In a letter to Nicaraguan Catholic priest, liberation theologian and politician Ernesto Cardenal (who entered Gethsemani but left in 1959 to study theology in Mexico), Merton¹³ wrote:"The world is full of great criminals with enormous power, and they are in a death struggle with each other. It is a huge gang battle, using well-meaning lawyers and policemen and clergymen as their front, controlling papers, means of communication, and enrolling everybody in their armies".¹⁴

Dante Alighieri aptly put it in the Divine Comedy: "In the middle of the journey of our life I came to myself within a dark wood where the straight way was lost. Ah, how hard a thing it is to tell what a wild, and rough, and stubborn wood this was, which in my thought renews the fear!"¹⁵.

A.Puskin writes in his *Demons*:

"All roads are skidded;

For the life of me, no trace is visible;

6 Esther *Etty* Hillesum (1914–1943) was the Dutch author of confessional letters and diaries which describe both her religious awakening and the persecutions of Jewish people in Amsterdam during the German occupation. In 1943 she was deported and killed in Auschwitz concentration camp.

7 Hillesum Etty, a diary note of 6 October (1941) in *An Interrupted Life: The Diaries of Etty Hillesum, 1941-1943* (1984)

8 Gabor Maté CM (1944) is a Hungarian-born Canadian physician. He has a background in family practice and a special interest in childhood development and trauma, and in their potential lifelong impacts on physical and mental health, including on autoimmune disease, cancer, ADHD, addictions, and a wide range of other conditions.

9 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ez2N%20ScXYZb4>

10 Zygmunt Bauman (1925–2017) was a Polish sociologist and philosopher. He was driven out of the Polish People's Republic during the 1968 Polish political crisis and forced to give up his Polish citizenship. He emigrated to Israel; three years later he moved to the United Kingdom. He resided in England from 1971, where he studied at the London School of Economics and became Professor of Sociology at the University of Leeds, later Emeritus. Bauman was a social theorist, writing on issues as diverse as modernity and the Holocaust, postmodern consumerism and liquid modernity.

11 Bauman Zygmunt (Autore) Braun-Vega Herman (Commento), Metzger Gustav (Commento), *Arte, ¿líquido?* (2007)

12 <https://hyperallergic.com/313435/an-illustrated-guide-to-guy-debords-the-society-of-the-spectacle/>

13 Robert King Merton (born Meyer Robert Schkolnick; 1910 – 2003) was an American sociologist who is considered a founding father of modern sociology, and a major contributor to the subfield of criminology. He served as the 47th President of the American Sociological Association. He spent most of his career teaching at Columbia University, where he attained the rank of University Professor. In 1994 he was awarded the National Medal of Science for his contributions to the field and for having founded the sociology of science.

14 Letter, November 17, 1962, quoted in Monica Furlong's *Merton: a Biography*, 263 (1995).

15 *Inferno* Cantos I-VII, <https://www.poetryintranslation.com/PITBR/Italian/DantInf1to7.php>

We got lost. What should we do!"¹⁶

For two weeks,¹⁷ leaders from almost 200 countries around the world have convened in Scotland with a mandate of nothing less than to save humanity from climate catastrophe, to find the way. The 26th Conference of the Parties of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, or COP26, is the latest in a series of annual meetings aiming to provide a global direction for climate action.

The stakes could not be higher.

Yes, the decisions made at this conference and in the next decade will dictate the future of life on this planet and civilization as we know it.¹⁸

Yes, the next few years will decide whether the millions suffering today will become billions. It will decide how many will get sick from the spreading of existing and new diseases. It will decide how extensive the crop losses and food shortages will be. It will decide the degree of conflict and violence and suffering.¹⁹

Yes, this is the weight on leaders' shoulders.²⁰

But what is about ourselves? Everyone has an opinion on what is wrong with the world, yet few will do the work to improve it.

Yes, there is the best-case scenario for the world as COP26 end. Get there first. You can't lead others until you first lead yourself. Start with yourself.

"Everyone thinks of changing the world, but no one thinks of changing himself,"²¹ - Leo Tolstoy said.

"Know thyself"²² is the main motto, inscribed on the pediment of the temple of Apollo at Delphi.

There are the ancient Egyptian sayings: "Man, know thyself, and thou shalt know the Gods.", "The body is the temple of the God within you; therefore it is said, 'Man: know thyself."²³

Selected verses from the Katha Upanishad announce: "Those who realize the Self are forever free from the jaws of death." "Know thyself to be pure and immortal!"²⁴

"To know thyself is the beginning of wisdom,²⁵" - Socrates was sure.

Jesus said: "He who knows the all, (but) fails (to know) himself, misses everything."²⁶

As it's written in Koran: "He who knows himself knows God".²⁷

"Knowing others is intelligence; knowing yourself is true wisdom. Mastering others is strength; mastering yourself is true power,"²⁸ - Lao Tzu confirms.

"This is true knowledge, to seek the Self as the true end of wisdom always. To seek anything else is ignorance,"²⁹ - is written in the Chapter 13, Verse 11 – Bhagavad Gita, The Song of God.

16 Puskin A.S. Demons, 1830, <https://kp-tts.ru/en/mchatsya-tuchi-novyi-grazhdanin-poet-besy.html>

17 From 31 October 2021 till 12 November 2021

18 <https://www.politico.com/news/magazine/2021/11/11/cop-26-climate-future-520817>

19 Ibid

20 Ibid

21 <https://energycentral.com/c/pip/%E2%80%9Ceveryone-thinks-changing-world-no-one-thinks-changing-himself%E2%80%9D-%E2%80%95-leo-tolstoy>

22 The motto γνώθι σεαυτόν () was one of the maxims inscribed on the pediment of the temple of Apollo at Delphi, along with μηδὲν ἄγαν ("nothing in excess"), inviting mankind to exercise moderation in life.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Know_thyself

23 <https://arkintime.com/know-thyself/ancient-egypt/>

24 <https://know-the-self.tumblr.com/post/183867936365/katha-upanishad-selected-verses-nachiketa>

25 <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/452128-to-know-thyself-is-the-beginning-of-wisdom#:~:text=Quote%20by%20Socrates%3A%20%E2%80%9Cto%20know,is%20the%20beginning%20of%20wisdom.%E2%80%9D>

26 Gospel of Thomas Saying 67

27 <https://islam.ru/en/content/story/he-who-knows-himself-knows-god>

28 <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/2979-knowing-others-is-intelligence-knowing-yourself-is-true-wisdom-mastering>

29 <https://erenow.net/common/the-bhagavad-gita-classics-of-indian-spirituality/15.php>

Gospel of Thomas, Saying 3, defines: "When you come to know yourselves, then you will become known, and you will realize that it is you who are the sons of the living father. But if you will not know yourselves, you dwell in poverty and it is you who are that poverty."³⁰

"All the scriptures tell us one thing: 'Know thyself.' If you have known yourself, you have known everything else,"³¹- is Satchidananda quote.

"Man know thyself; then thou shalt know the Universe and God,"³²- Pythagoras said.

The following words are written on the tomb of an Anglican bishop in the crypts of Westminster Abbey:

"When I was young and free and my imagination had no limits, I dreamed of changing the world.

As I grew older and wiser, I discovered the world would not change, so I shortened my sights somewhat and decided to change only my country. But it too seemed immovable.

As I grew into my twilight years, in one last desperate attempt, I settled for changing only my family, those closest to me, but alas, they would have none of it.

And now as I lay on my deathbed, I suddenly realize: If I had only changed myself first, then by example, I would have changed my family.

From their inspiration and encouragement, I would then have been able to better my country and, who knows, I may have even changed the world."³³

Everyone would like to live in a better world, to have well-being, to be healthy and happy, yet few will work to change themselves. Most people are frustrated or angry with climate change and other circumstances beyond their control. They would like to achieve a better life by reforming state structures. They believe if states can control these situations they are happy. "It's like the people who believe they'll be happy if they go and live somewhere else, but who learn it doesn't work that way. Wherever you go, you take yourself with you." (Neil Gaiman³⁴).

The current crisis is attributed to the politics, the finance, the economy, the legislation, the judiciary. Instead, it is necessary to go further upstream, to a human being, to one who acts in politics, economy, executive power, judiciary and to think of the form of humanity, where Nature is protected, human rights and justice are really achieved and are not proclaimed only. If you want to change reality start with yourself first and attend to your personal development. It was John C. Maxwell³⁵ who wrote: "How You (Yes, You!) Can Change the World"³⁶.

If we change, the world change. It is necessary to attend to our own personal development. It is futile trying to change conditions out. It makes sense to work on ourselves. Albert Einstein recognised this principle when he said: "The problems that exist in the world today cannot be solved by the level of thinking that created them"³⁷. It's an inside-out job. Dag Hammarskjöld³⁸ in his Markings³⁹ (1963) wrote: "Our work for peace

30 <https://www.marquette.edu/maqom/Gospel%20of%20Thomas%20Lambdin.pdf>

31 <https://www.poetseers.org/spiritual-and-devotional-poets/india/swami-satchidananda/satchidananda-quotes/>

32 <https://quotefancy.com/quote/1374558/Pythagoras-Man-know-thyself-then-thou-shalt-know-the-Universe-and-God#:~:text=Pythagoras%20Quote%3A%20%E2%80%9CMan%20know%20thyself,known%20the%20Universe%20and%20God.%E2%80%9D>

33 <https://www.collegiate-empowerment.org/blog/8/10/2015/start-with-yourself>

34 Neil Richard MacKinnon Gaiman (born Neil Richard Gaiman, 1960) is an English author of short fiction, novels, comic books, graphic novels, nonfiction, audio theatre, and films. He has won numerous awards, including the Hugo, Nebula, and Bram Stoker awards, as well as the Newbery and Carnegie medals. He is the first author to win both the Newbery and the Carnegie medals for the same work, *The Graveyard Book* (2008). In 2013, *The Ocean at the End of the Lane* was voted Book of the Year in the British National Book Awards.

35 John Calvin Maxwell (born 1947) is an American author, speaker, and pastor who has written many books, primarily focusing on leadership. Titles include *The 21 Irrefutable Laws of Leadership* and *The 21 Indispensable Qualities of a Leader*. His books have sold millions of copies, with some on the New York Times Best Seller List.

36 <https://www.johnmaxwell.com/blog/how-you-yes-you-can-change-the-world/>

37 https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/albert_einstein_121993; In *The New Quotable Einstein*, Alice Calaprice suggests that this phrase attributed to Einstein could be a paraphrase of two quotes from a 1946 article.

must begin within the private world of each of us. To build for man a world without fear, we must be without fear. To build a world of justice, we must be just".⁴⁰

We don't have to change the world. We share Vishen Lakhiani⁴¹'s opinion that "too many people trap themselves in the chains of realistic goals because they refuse to see beyond the HOW. Don't worry about the HOW. Start with the WHAT and the WHY. When you know what you want to bring forth in the world and WHY you want it, choose it. Then take whatever action intuition guides you toward taking."⁴²

Let's borrow the words from Ch.Dickens: "It was the best of times, it was the worst of times, it was the age of wisdom, it was the age of foolishness, it was the epoch of belief, it was the epoch of incredulity, it was the season of Light, it was the season of Darkness, it was the spring of hope, it was the winter of despair, we had everything before us, we had nothing before us, we were all going direct to Heaven, we were all going direct the other way – in short, the period was so far like the present period, that some of its noisiest authorities insisted on its being received, for good or for evil, in the superlative degree of comparison only".⁴³

We don't need to change the world, we need to raise our level of consciousness.

We just have to change what we pay attention to in the world. And that, it turns out, is hugely powerful.

We don't have to change the world

We don't need to find our way

We can stay right here, lay back, relax

Let the sun just chase our blues away

Let the planets spin around a few thousand times

Let the madness and the pressure and the monday lives.

(Georgina Callaghan⁴⁴)

38 Dag Hjalmar Agne Carl Hammarskjöld (1905–1961) was a Swedish diplomat, economist, writer and public official. He was president of the Bank of Sweden, but became known internationally as UN Secretary-General. He held the position for two consecutive terms, from 1953 until his death in 1961, which occurred due to a plane crash in southern Africa during a mission of peace. He became a role model in moral leadership to most of his successors and many more people all over the world. Both in his work and in his speeches he promoted an attitude of international service. He was posthumously awarded the Nobel Peace Prize for his humanitarian activity. U.S. President John F. Kennedy called Hammarskjöld *the greatest statesman of our century*. (Linnér, Sture; Åström, Sverker. UN Secretary-General Hammarskjöld: Reflections and Personal Experiences (The 2007 Dag Hammarskjöld Lecture). Uppsala University, 28 (2008). This is the translated text of the 2007 Dag Hammarskjöld Lecture given by Sture Linnér and Sverker Åström at Uppsala University on 15 October 2007, http://www.daghammarskjold.se/wp-content/uploads/2007/10/Dh_lecture_2007.pdf

39 After the tragic death of UN Secretary-General Dag Hammarskjöld in 1961 his personal notes, Vägmärken, were translated into English and published in 1963 under the title Markings. The world was surprised that Hammarskjöld apparently had been a devout Christian. More details: Nylund Jan, Dag Hammarskjöld's Spirituality Revisited: A Critique of W.H. Auden's Understanding and Translation of Markings (January 2014), https://www.researchgate.net/publication/274384735_Dag_Hammarskjold's_Spirituality_Revisited_A_Critique_of_WH_Auden's_Understanding_and_Translation_of_Markings

40 Hammarskjöld Dag, UN Press Release SG/360, December 22, 1953.

41 Vishen Lakhiani, (born 1976) is a Malaysian entrepreneur, author, and motivational speaker, of Indian descent, he is one of the most influential personalities in personal growth today. A computer engineer and entrepreneur in education technology, he is the founder and CEO of Mindvalley, a 200-person-strong company that specializes in learning experience design and creating digital platforms and apps that power the education revolution. Mindvalley's curriculum focuses on personal growth, mindfulness, well-being, productivity, and more. He is also a member of the Transformational Leadership Council and sits on the Innovation Board for XPRIZE Foundation. Lakhiani's mission is to revolutionize the global education system through new models for enhancing human potential and building a school for Humanity 2.0.

42 Lakhiani Vishen, *The Code of the Extraordinary Mind: 10 Unconventional Laws to Redefine Your Life and Succeed On Your Own Terms* (2016), <https://www.goodreads.com/work/quotes/46061394-the-code-of-the-extraordinary-mind-10-unconventional-laws-to-redefine-y>

43 Dickens Charles, *A Tale of Two Cities* (1859), https://en.wikiquote.org/wiki/A_Tale_of_Two_Cities

44 Georgina Callaghan is a British singer-songwriter. She performs under the name Callaghan. She is best known for her 2012 album *Life in Full Colour* produced by Shawn Mullins. <https://callaghansongs.com/home>

"You can cut all the flowers but you cannot keep spring from coming,"⁴⁵ - Pablo Neruda is sure.. "You will not become aware of the world you live in if you look at it with the same attention. So don't look, watch", -Dr Prem Jagyasi⁴⁶ is right.

In his "Ethics" Baruch Spinoza said: "The human mind has an adequate knowledge of the eternal and infinite essence of God."⁴⁷

It was the late Dr Wayne Dyer⁴⁸, who said: "If you change the way you look at things, the things you look at change."⁴⁹ He knew change must first take place from within and has a ripple effect outside. If that change is powerful enough, it will gather momentum to affect the whole of humanity.

We don't need to change the world, we need to upgrade our model of reality.

And it is with this knowledge in hand that we forward the idea to join up businesses and the climate/nature agendas, launching *Golden Hours Idea*, to arrive at an ambitious, measurable and accountable post-2021 global biodiversity framework in businesses.

Golden Hours are creative time for our well-being.

Some law firms today have already been making a meaningful change, designating "golden hours" in the day when employees can feel free to take a break and spend some time for their own well-being and not to feel constantly under pressure to neglect their mental health for the sake of the firm or their clients.⁵⁰

Many of you will have already heard about the 'Golden Hour' concept - various high-achievers advocate the idea.⁵¹ Brian Tracy and Dan Ariely⁵² have developed a method to manage productivity, called the "Golden Hour." In their theory, our peak productivity is reached within a specific time window after waking up.

Brian Tracy and Dan Ariely, both, agree that we are at our most productive at the beginning of our day, after we have woken up naturally. Our brain and energy level come together in a synchronized peak. This is when we should get things done —a moment we should use to the fullest. This hour of our day can make a difference between a productive day and a chaotic, energy-draining one.

We can wake up an hour earlier than usual and then fill our hour with 3 x 20 minutes segments of time, each dedicated to something that promotes self-improvement. For example, we may spend the first 20 minutes going for a walk/run, the next 20 minutes reading a book or article online and the last 20 minutes segment spending 20 minutes writing that novel we've always dreamed about.

We all know the benefits strengthening and conditioning practices like physical training and meditation have on both the mind and the body.

Finding the time everyday to focus on our personal health and well-being has been proven

45 <https://kidadl.com/articles/pablo-neruda-quotes-from-the-famous-poet-and-politician>

46 Dr Prem Jagyasi is an award-winning strategic leader, renowned author, publisher and highly acclaimed global speaker. Aside from publishing a bevy of life improvement guides, Dr Prem is also the author of Medical Tourism, Wellness Tourism, Carve Your Life – Live A Great Life Guide. He also runs a Guides and Magazine Network web magazine network of 50+ niche magazines that attract millions of readers across the globe.

<https://designbuzz.com/dr-prem-jagyasi/>

47 See in detail: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40231182>

48 Wayne Walter Dyer (1940 – 2015) was an American self-help and spiritual author and a motivational speaker. His first book, *Your Erroneous Zones* (1976), is one of the best-selling books of all time, with an estimated 100 million copies sold to date

49 <https://www.leadershipfirst.net/post/change-the-way-you-look-at-things-and-the-things-you-look-at-change#:~:text=Wayne%20Dyer%20once%20said%2C%20%E2%80%9CChange,it%20was%20designed%20to%20be.>

50 <https://www.law.com/americanlawyer/2021/05/03/lawyers-were-already-struggling-with-stress-and-isolation-and-the-pandemic-has-made-things-much-worse/>

51 <https://www.upscalinglife.com/utilizing-your-golden-hour-for-peak-productivity/>

52 Time-management expert Brian Tracy was the first to use the term "Golden Hour" in this context — a concept referred to in many time-management theories. Tracy refers to a one-hour period, but Dan Ariely refers to a period of two hours in which productivity peaks. <https://www.upscalinglife.com/utilizing-your-golden-hour-for-peak-productivity/>

to support our mind, our physical health, keep our stress levels in check and as a result strengthen our respiratory and immune systems.

It really is up to us how we divide the 60-90 minutes of time. By spending even just 15 minutes everyday can really help us to keep health and wellbeing as a priority throughout our day and adds an extra 105 minutes of time to focus on our well being every week! "The physical body is a temple. Take care of it. The mind is energy. Regulate it. The soul is the projection. Represent it. All knowledge is false if the soul is not experienced in the body,"⁵³ - Yogi Bhajan⁵⁴ says.

The aim of our Golden Hours Idea is to establish new legal tools for protection efforts, to build new institutional and decision-making arrangements to promote effective policy in businesses and physical persons, at a national and a supra-national levels.

To secure nature is to invest in ourselves.

We don't need to change the world, we need to improve our productivity. "Man is a personality not by nature but by spirit. By nature he is only an individual",⁵⁵- Berdyaev⁵⁶ wrote. Men in addition to being endowed with the dimension that pertains to the body (bios and zoè⁵⁷), also have the dimension of the spirit.

According to our Golden Hours theory, our peak productivity is reached within a specific time/space window linked with our "awakening".

Meditation is a priceless tool for attaining this knowledge because it is an inner looking practice. It helps us to see what's really going on within our hearts and minds. It also helps us to realize the truth of reality. And as the great Carl Jung said, "Your vision will become clear only when you can look into your own heart. Who looks outside, dreams; who looks inside, awakes"⁵⁸. The intellect is only a means of opening the way to direct mystical experience, which is called *Awakening*.

Paul Knitter⁵⁹ says: "To have a mystical or personal religious experience is to feel oneself connected with, part of, united with, aware of, one with, Something or Some-activity larger than oneself. One feels transported beyond one's usual sense of self as one grows aware of an expanded self, or a loss of self, in the discovery of something beyond words.

Philosopher of religion John Hick⁶⁰ describes mystical experience as the shift from self-centeredness to Other-centeredness or Reality-centeredness. Certainly, our description of Buddhist Enlightenment squares with this unitive characteristic of mysticism, even though

53 <https://www.harinam.com/today-the-physical-body-is-a-temple-take-care-of-it-yogi-bhajan/>

54 Harbhajan Singh Khalsa (born as Harbhajan Singh Puri (1929–2004), also known as Yogi Bhajan and Siri Singh Sahib to his followers, was an Indian-born-American yoga teacher, spiritual teacher, and entrepreneur. He introduced his version of Kundalini Yoga to the United States. He was the spiritual director of the 3HO (Healthy, Happy, Holy Organization) Foundation, with over 300 centers in 35 countries.

55 Berdyaev N, Slavery and Freedom,(1939) 21

56 Nikolai Alexandrovich Berdyaev (1874–1948) was a Russian political and Christian religious philosopher who emphasized the existential spiritual significance of human freedom and the human person.

57 βίος (bíos): indicates the conditions, the ways in which our life takes place. Zoé is therefore the life that is in us and through which we live (qua vivimus), bios alludes to the way we live (quam vivimus), that is, the modalities that characterize, for example, contemplative life, political life, etc. for which the Greek language uses the term bios accompanied by a qualifying adjective; (Martin Heidegger, Fundamental concepts of Aristotelian philosophy, (Italian) Milano, Adelphi, (2017) 77

58 <https://philosiblog.com/2011/09/05/your-vision-will-become-clear-only-when-you-can-look-into-your-own-heart-who-looks-outside-dreams-who-looks-inside-awakes/#:~:text=knowledge%2C%20value%2C%20vision-,Your%20vision%20will%20become%20clear%20only%20when%20you%20can%20look,%E2%80%93Carl%20Jung>

59 Paul Francis Knitter (1939) is an American theologian, known for his work on religious pluralism and multiple religious belonging, particularly regarding Buddhism and Christianity.

60 John Harwood Hick (1922 – 2012) was a philosopher of religion and theologian born in England who taught in the United States for the larger part of his career. In philosophical theology, he made contributions in the areas of theodicy, eschatology, and Christology, and in the philosophy of religion he contributed to the areas of epistemology of religion and religious pluralism.

Buddhists, while strong on loss of self, use deliberately slippery terms for what they're connected with: Emptiness, Groundlessness, InterBeing. Christian mystics, on the other hand, are very clear about what they are united with. Christian mystical literature abounds with expressions such as one with Christ, temples of the Holy Spirit, the Body of Christ, Spouses of Christ, the Divine indwelling, participants in the divine nature".⁶¹

With our *Golden Hours Idea* we remind about the importance of Nature.

We invite everyone to begin with a necessary understanding where we have come from, where we are (*D'où venons nous? Que sommes nous? Où allons nous?*⁶², the French painter Gauguine asked also) and so on, and above all where we laugh, to arrive at the inevitable conclusion that until now we have not behaved as good ancestors, we have created the conditions for an environmental injustice that will be paid for by the next generations.

We invite you to turn to Spinoza's idea that the world is part of God with the distinction between God and the world. God and the world are not two different entities, he argues, but two different aspects of a single reality. The monist philosophical system of Baruch Spinoza- Spinozism (also spelled Spinozism)- defines "God" as a singular self-subsistent substance, with both matter and thought being attributes of such.⁶³ In a letter to Henry Oldenburg, Spinoza wrote: "as to the view of certain people that I identify god with nature (taken as a kind of mass or corporeal matter), they are quite mistaken".⁶⁴

For Spinoza, our universe (cosmos) is a mode under infinite attributes, of which we can perceive two: Thought and Extension. God has infinitely many other attributes which are not present in our world.

We take Spinoza's philosophy because it is practical through and through. His ideas are never merely intellectual constructions, but lead directly to a certain way of life. This is evidenced by the fact that his greatest work, which combines metaphysics, theology, epistemology, and human psychology, is called Ethics. In this book, Spinoza argues that the way to "blessedness" or "salvation" for each person involves an expansion of the mind towards an intuitive understanding of God, of the whole of nature and its laws. In other words, philosophy for Spinoza is like a spiritual practice, whose goal is happiness and liberation.

Our *Golden Hours* philosophy is to feel the same force in us that makes a stem live.

"The force that through the green fuse drives the flower

Drives my green age"⁶⁵- Dylan Thomas felt⁶⁶

It is our prana, our vital force that sustains not only the body but also the mind:

- it means making the connection to life through natural rhythms;
- it means having the sense of a great and strong communion that runs through the entire creation and makes us united in the Whole;
- it means abandoning oneself to the Whole as the stem does, which offers no resistance,
- it means to urge it and push it forward;
- it means knowing how to enter the dynamics of life, of the harmonious relationship;

61 Knitter Paul F, Without Buddha I Could Not be a Christian (2009)

62 https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Gauguin_-_D'o%C3%9C%27ou_venons-nous_Que_sommes-nous_Ou_allons-nous.jpg

63 Nadler Steven, "Baruch Spinoza: God or Nature". In Zalta, Edward N. (ed.). Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. The Metaphysics Research Lab, Center for the Study of Language and Information, Stanford University. (Summer 2020), <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/spinoza/#GodNatu>

64 Correspondence of Benedict de Spinoza, Wilder Publications (March 26, 2009), ISBN 1-60459-156-0, letter 73

65 <https://poets.org/poem/force-through-green-fuse-drives-flower>

66 Dylan Marlais Thomas (1914 –1953) was a Welsh poet and writer whose works include the poems "Do not go gentle into that good night" and "And death shall have no dominion"; the "play for voices" Under Milk Wood; and stories and radio broadcasts such as A Child's Christmas in Wales and Portrait of the Artist as a Young Dog.

- it means to use our *human navel point*⁶⁷, that's according to Yogi Bhajan, "sometimes misunderstood, but it is the most active point in the entire body".⁶⁸

When we pump our navel energy or move from our navel center we are actually pumping and moving from a center where thousands of nerves come together. Practice of any of the martial arts will help you find and align this center of gravity in your body.

By nature we participate in all events, we are intertwined with them in a magnificent warp. We discover interconnection of all things and phenomena of the universe, sensed since the dawn of time. If we just abandon ourselves to meditation and let our thinking go deeper, we feel an intimate connection, we feel we are part of the Whole.

Science then tells us that there is no particle that is lost or consumed, but everything flows from one use to another. "A human being is a part of the whole called by us universe, a part limited in time and space. He experiences himself, his thoughts and feeling as something separated from the rest, a kind of optical delusion of his consciousness. This delusion is a kind of prison for us, restricting us to our personal desires and to affection for a few persons nearest to us. Our task must be to free ourselves from this prison by widening our circle of compassion to embrace all living creatures and the whole of nature in its beauty."⁶⁹— Albert Einstein said.

During this changing period of our lives, we argue that finding the time to fit in daily segments of time that are dedicated to meditation and exercising our bodies, is more important than ever.. "Nothing exists in the universe that is not in the human body, nothing exists in the human body that is not in the universe."⁷⁰ We live thanks to the communication between the body, the mind (soul) and the Spirit (consciousness, the Whole). This communication goes every instant, every thousandth of an instant, in thousands of our cells, among tens of thousands of molecules: a constant, infinitesimal and infinite communication of aromas, signals, vibrations, information. Our body, our mind and Spirit (the Whole) are interconnected. "The rainbow clearly doesn't end on the horizon for me, but in my soul. And for right now, my soul has found a little peace"- Pablo Neruda knew well about this communication..⁷¹ It is an unconscious life, it's constant, it's under our rational and conscious life. It means much more than Web, our mobile phones and chat, an intelligent network. For us it's more important than the digitalization. The secrets of change, birth, death and healing dwell in this communication between our body, our mind and the Spirit (the Whole).

"We are all spiritual being having a physical experience".⁷² "We are the product of our thoughts, attitudes and actions lived in this huge simulator that is the Universe",-says Tiller⁷³. In this simulator a man is mortal from the body point of view, but essentially indestructible from the point of view of consciousness.⁷⁴

67 https://www.kundaliniyoga.org/lesson_10

68 "This is what the scriptures say. Human grows to life (in the womb) without the breath of life (because the prana comes from the mother) through the navel point. The only energy you had was at the navel point. That is why we stimulate the navel. In Kundalini Yoga there are two points that we stir up: one is the pituitary and the other is the navel point",-Yogi Bhajan, quoted in <http://lakshminarayanlenasia.com/articles/Praana-Praanee-Praanayam-Harijot-Kaur-Khalsa.pdf>

69 <https://www.nytimes.com/1972/03/29/archives/the-einstein-papers-a-man-of-many-parts-the-einstein-papers-man-of.html>

70 Quoted in Medicina Quantistica, by Franco Frascini. <https://www.macrolibrarsi.it/speciali/prefazione-anatomia-della-coscienza-quantica-libro-di-erica-francesca-poli.php>

71 <https://www.goodreads.com/work/quotes/279794-el-libro-de-las-preguntas>

72 On the phrase see: <https://quoteinvestigator.com/2019/06/20/spiritual/>

73 William A. Tiller is emeritus professor of Science and Engineering of Materials, at Stanford University. Tiller spent 34 years in academia, after having been a consultative physicist at Westinghouse Research Laboratories for nine years, he has published over 250 scientific papers.

74 <https://www.filosofiaelogos.it/News/Siamo-esseri-spirituali-rivestiti-di-un-Bio-Corpo.html>

Hans Urs von Balthasar⁷⁵ said that “the greatest enigma that there is in man is that he is two things at the same time: a nature (that is, a spiritual soul incarnated in a body, an individual) and a person (incomparable, eternal uniqueness)”.⁷⁶

Men don't have two detached and distinct dimensions, but human beings have a magnificent integration of some friend areas that transform and elevate themselves. "The truth is that the human body is made up of ten bodies: the physical body, three mental bodies, and six energy bodies. The eleventh embodiment – when all ten bodies are under your direction – produces a pure state of consciousness when you have the ability to see all events as God's Play and recognize the God in all.

You can visualize your various bodies as layers of clothing, the physical body being the overcoat you wear for a lifetime. We know we have a physical body; we can see it, touch it, and feel it. We also have other bodies that are equally real, if not more so.”⁷⁷

Everything is made of waves; also, particles. There's lots of places to start this sort of discussion, and this is as good as any: everything in the universe has both particle and wave nature, at the same time. All is waves, everything in the universe has wave nature. Of course, everything in the universe also has particle nature. This the rational mind cannot conceive.

Modern human body, mind (emotions),⁷⁸ conscience (consciousness, spirit, the Whole)⁷⁹ are as Krylov's Swan, Pike and Cancer⁸⁰ or Gurdjieff's rider, charioteer, horse and cart.⁸¹ When human right to life becomes more important than life, nature when religion becomes more important than conscience (thought), when religious practice with its external aspects becomes more important than internal motivations and love, it is good to return to the essential.

75 Hans Urs von Balthasar (1905–1988) was a Swiss theologian and Catholic priest, unique among the great Central European theologians. He has produced a vast theological work, which can be considered among the most influential of the twentieth century and has since found many interpreters in contemporary theological research. His theology was influenced by his contacts with Jesuits, philosophers and theologians, such as Erich Przywara, Jean Daniélou and Henri de Lubac. With his activity as a lecturer and his numerous publications he contributed to a renewed interest in patristics, making it available again to theology and the Christian faith. Von Balthasar is considered among the greatest Catholic theologians of the twentieth century, together with Karl Rahner, Henri de Lubac, Romano Guardini and others.

76 On the issue see: Harrison Victoria S, Personal Identity And Integration: Von Balthasar's Phenomenology Of Human Holiness, *The Heythrop Journal*, 40(4):424 - 437 (December 2002)

77 From *The Aquarian Teacher: KRI Teacher Training Level One Manual*

<https://www.3ho.org/kundalini-yoga/ten-bodies>

78 During the past 30 years, Antonio R. Damasio has strived to show that feelings are what arise as the brain interprets emotions, which are themselves purely physical signals of the body reacting to external stimuli. Researchers study the mind-body connection and scientifically demonstrate Mind-Body Connection.

79 Or physical, astral, mental, causal bodies.

80 Swan, Pike and Cancer is a fable of Ivan Andreevich Krylov, written in 1814 and published in the collection *New Fables* (1816, part 4). The plot contains a hint of the events of that time: the dissatisfaction of the Russian society with the actions of the political allies of Emperor Alexander I (the war of the Sixth Coalition against Napoleon); according to another version, contemporaries associated the plot of the fable with disagreements between members of the State Council. (*Big Encyclopedic Dictionary*, ed. Brockhaus F. A. and Efron I. A. (1890-1907) (Russian),

https://naurok.su/bio/rus/Krylov_Ivan_Andreevich/;

<https://wikibath.ru/en/krylov-kogda-v-tovarishchah-soglasya-net-vyrazhenie-a-voz-i-nyne.html>

81 Gurdjieff says: “Man is like a rig consisting of passenger, driver, horse and carriage” in Gurdjieff G. I, *Views From the Real World*, http://www.giurfa.com/real_world.pdf . See Nicoll Maurice, *Psychological Commentaries on the Teaching of Gurdjieff and Ouspensky*, Volume 3,

http://www.gianfrancobertagni.it/materiali/gurdjieff/nicoll_commentari3.pdf

A human being must harmonise, synchronize⁸² his *three brains*⁸³.

A human being must seek his neutral Mind. A Man has to climb to a higher floor than the one inhabited by most modern people. A plan that belongs to him, but it is little practiced, is the dimension of the spirit. It is here the human rights (freedoms), common good become such. The lower floors are colored by private interest, lobbies, political parties. They become personal success. If the human rights, freedoms, the common good, recognized by all, fail on the lower floors, it is because of lack of understanding that the rights, freedoms of human beings, their common good are not something to be placed in a showcase that decorates the room, they are not ethical, but must be a mentality, a particular and precious interior attitude that can be realized only in the dimension of the spirit. The common good must guide action, give substance to it. However, the dimension of the spirit isn't an individual living, it develops together, it is the attitude of openness, doing things with a disposition towards what is greater.⁸⁴ The Hindu tradition, Katha Upanishad sets: "Know the Self as lord of the chariot, the body as the chariot itself, the discriminating intellect as charioteer, and the mind as reins. The senses, say the wise, are the horses; selfish desires are the roads they travel".⁸⁵

We don't need to change the world, we need to try to understand.

Could be a modern professor who calls on a journey beyond traditional science welcomed into the scientific community?

Yes, he could and he has to be welcomed, because the true view does not look around for the mistake that someone has made, but for some idea that a scientist has shown in the furrows of the world to solve the problem and *the problems that exist in the world today cannot be solved by the level of thinking that created them.*

We like this scientific community to which solving the problem, finding a solution matter even more than fidelity to some traditional idea of science, which places society, its problems before ideas of science, which welcomes our ideas too. We like a scientist who is such not only in his greatness but also in his humanity. The mistakes teach us. "They teach us something instead, I believe, about the nature of intelligence"⁸⁶, - says Carlo Rovelli⁸⁷. Intelligence is not about stubborn adherence to your own opinions. It requires

82 In G.I. Gurdjieff's *Fourth Way*, centers or brains refer to separate apparatuses within a being that dictate its specific functions. According to this teaching, there are three main centers: intellectual, emotional, and moving. These centers in the human body are analogous to a three-storey factory, the intellectual center being the top storey, the emotional center being the middle one, and the moving center being the bottom storey. The moving center, or the bottom storey is further divided into three separate functions: sex, instinctive, and motor.

Gurdjieff classified plants as having one brain, animals two and humans three brains. In *Beelzebub's Tales to His Grandson*, Gurdjieff greatly expanded his idea of humans as *three brained beings*.

In the book *The Fourth Way*, Ouspensky refers to the *center of gravity* as being a center which different people primarily operate from (intellectuals, artists, and sports enthusiasts, for example, might represent each of these centers). See Ouspensky, P. D., *The Fourth Way*, Vintage new edition (February 1971)

83 We have three brains – our HEAD brain, our HEART brain, and our GUT brain: the intellect which resides in the head, the moving-instinctive brain which resides in the spine and the emotional brain which is centered in the solar plexus, but disperse to some degree throughout the abdomen. The three brains are like an orchestra, with billions of neurons cooperating to produce a harmonic symphony – harnessing together an ever-changing network of neurons that work in synchrony. It knows as Eastern thought (Dantian or simply *energy center*. Dantian are the *qi focus flow centers*, important focal points for meditative and exercise techniques such as qigong, martial arts such as t'ai chi ch'uan, and in traditional Chinese medicine) as West one. <https://www.goodnet.org/articles/head-heart-gut-how-to-use-3-brains>
On their influence on decision-making see Soosalu Grant Henwood Suzanne, Deo Arun, Head, Heart, and Gut in *Decision Making: Development of a Multiple Brain Preference Questionnaire* (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019837439>

84 See on the issue: Riley Clare Valentine, *An Impersonal Liberalism: Simone Weil and the Sacred*, <https://epochmagazine.org/an-impersonal-liberalism-simone-weil-and-the-sacred-6843f9794f85>

85 <https://www.bmcm.org/inspiration/passages/razors-edge/>

86 <https://inews.co.uk/news/science/carlo-rovelli-making-mistakes-sign-of-intelligence-einsteins-errors-757427>

87 Carlo Rovelli is an internationally renowned theoretical physicist who during his career has worked mainly in the field of quantum gravity and was one of the founders of the theory of loop quantum gravity. Carlo Rovelli also deals with the history and philosophy of science. In *Helgoland* Rovelli delves into revolutionary theory, first allowing us to

readiness to change and even discard those opinions. In order to understand the world, you need to have the courage to experiment with ideas, not to fear failure, to constantly revise your opinions, to make them work better: "The Einstein who makes more errors than anyone else is precisely the same Einstein who succeeds in understanding more about nature than anyone else, and these are complementary and necessary aspects of the same profound intelligence: the audacity of thought, the courage to take risks, the lack of faith in received ideas – including, crucially, one's own".⁸⁸ Because what's important is not being right. It's to try to understand. Try to understand. Criticism of understanding (*Critica del capire* (1942) is the beautiful book's title of an almost unknown Italian philosopher of the twentieth century Luigi Scaravelli.⁸⁹

Lawrence Pearsall Jacks⁹⁰ wrote: "A master in the art of living draws no sharp distinction between his work and his play; his labor and his leisure; his mind and his body; his education and his recreation. He hardly knows which is which. He simply pursues his vision of excellence through whatever he is doing, and leaves others to determine whether he is working or playing. To himself, he always appears to be doing both."⁹¹

What's important is a choice of true *Thinking Hat*.⁹²

We don't need to change the world, we need to make healthy changes in our eating habits.

The modern age is beset by the fundamental problem: "The problem is what faiths the modern world feeds on and subsists on; what is the authentic faith that sustains him in life that gives him the strength of activity and the conviction of participating with his life (or his action or his being) in immortality, that is, in the absolute? Every man needs the absolute and therefore his problem is the participation in the absolute "⁹³ - great Andrea Emo⁹⁴ wrote.

Turn the problem into an occasion,
Change your way of thinking,

understand its theoretical and practical value, and then exploring the issues that make quantum theory one of the most mysterious physical theories science has to do with. These mysteries have been at the center of the research of physicists, philosophers and other great thinkers for years: Rovelli focuses on the relational interpretation and on the links between this interpretation and oriental history, art, literature and philosophy. The author leads to discover how this view of quantum theory can lead us to reconsider the way in which we think about reality.

88 Rovelli Carlo, There are places in the world where kindness is more important than rules, *Corriere della Sera* (2018)

89 Luigi Scaravelli (1894 - 1957) was an Italian philosopher. He comes to philosophy after studying medicine, mathematics and music, the interests that also re-emerge in his detailed analyzes of classical thinkers: Plato, Descartes, Kant, Hegel, Croce, Heidegger. Scientists remember him as "a free, light-hearted Tuscan", "immune from any pedantic gravity", capable of "reducing an entire system to an essential formula of logic".

90 Lawrence Pearsall Jacks (1860 – 1955), abbreviated L. P. Jacks, was an English educator, philosopher, and Unitarian minister who rose to prominence in the period from World War I to World War II.

91 Jacks Lawrence Pearsall, *Education through Recreation* (1932), 1.

https://en.wikiquote.org/wiki/L._P._Jacks#:~:text=his%20Hibbert%20Lecture.-,A%20master%20in%20the%20ar%20of%20living%20draws%20no%20sharp,his%20education%20and%20his%20recreation.

92 Six Thinking Hats was written by Dr. Edward de Bono. *Six Thinking Hats* and the associated idea parallel thinking provide a means to plan thinking processes in a detailed and cohesive way. It's a powerful technique for looking at decision making from different points of view. It allows emotion and skepticism to be brought into what might normally be a purely rational process, and it opens up the opportunity for creativity within decision making. See De Bono, Edward, *Six Thinking Hats: An Essential Approach to Business Management*. Little, Brown, & Company. (1985)

93 *Quaderni di metafisica*. 1927-1981, a cura di Massimo Donà e Romano Gasparotti, pref. di Massimo Cacciari, contributi di Enrico Ghezzi, Giulio Giorello, Laura Sanò, Carlo Sini, Vincenzo Vitiello, Francesco Tomatis e Andrea Tagliapietra. Bompiani, Milano (2006).

<http://www.cristinacampo.it/public/intervista%20a%20massimo%20don%20c3%20a0%20su%20emo%20di%20l.pdf>

94 Andrea Emo Capodilista (1901-1983) was an Italian philosopher. Born in an aristocratic family from Venice, he studied in the University of Rome and was student of Giovanni Gentile but he never graduated. Anyway he developed a personal and original philosophy that remained unpublished till 1986 when philosopher Massimo Cacciari found hundreds of his booknotes and started publishing it.

He lived all his life alone in an almost ascetic and spartan life, his few friends were writers Alberto Savinio, Ugo Spirito and poet Cristina Campo.

Shake hands with your mind and spirit,
And enjoy for the sake of your uniqueness.
And laugh!
Enjoy the bio-body you have.
Unite them three!
Eat the subtle energy that you create day after day
and if necessary - share that subtle energy - ...
May those around you *eat and drink* you!

A famous statement by the German philosopher Ludwig Feuerbach is: *Der Mensch ist, was er ißt.* (man is what he eats).⁹⁵ But even before him, in 1826, the French lawyer Anthelme Brillat-Savarin wrote, in *Physiologie du Gout, ou Meditations de Gastronomie Transcendante*:

“Dis-moi ce que tu manges, je te dirai ce que tu es. (Tell me what you eat and I will tell you what you are)”.⁹⁶ In his Easter Sermon, 227, St. Augustine exhorted: “we become what we receive”.⁹⁷

Our Golden Hours Idea is for the creation of relationships with absolute and established values, to incline the Mediterranean lifestyle⁹⁸ around the world. Mediterranean diet was inscribed in 2013 on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity

The Mediterranean diet involves a set of skills, knowledge, rituals, symbols and traditions concerning crops, harvesting, fishing, animal husbandry, conservation, processing, cooking, and particularly the sharing and consumption of food. Eating together is the foundation of the cultural identity and continuity of communities throughout the Mediterranean basin. It is a moment of social exchange and communication, an affirmation and renewal of family, group or community identity. The Mediterranean diet emphasizes values of hospitality, neighbourliness, intercultural dialogue and creativity, and a way of life guided by respect for diversity. It plays a vital role in cultural spaces, festivals and celebrations, bringing together people of all ages, conditions and social classes. It includes the craftsmanship and production of traditional receptacles for the transport, preservation and consumption of food, including ceramic plates and glasses. Women play an important role in transmitting knowledge of the Mediterranean diet: they safeguard its techniques, respect seasonal rhythms and festive events, and transmit the values of the element to new generations. Markets also play a key role as spaces for cultivating and transmitting the Mediterranean diet during the daily practice of exchange, agreement and mutual respect.

A true way of life, the Mediterranean diet is good for health as well as bringing social, economic and environmental benefits.⁹⁹

A study published in 2013 in the journal *Environmental Health* found if Spaniards chose a Mediterranean diet over a Western one, greenhouse gas emissions would be reduced by 72 percent, land use by 58 percent, and energy consumption by 52 percent.¹⁰⁰ It is definitely recognized as a sustainable lifestyle. According to FAO, “Sustainable diets are

95 More details: Cherno Melvin, Feuerbach's "Man is what He Eats": A Rectification, *Journal of the History of Ideas*, Vol. 24, No. 3, 397-406 (Jul. - Sep., 1963)

96 More details <https://www.phrases.org.uk/meanings/you-are-what-you-eat.html>

97 <https://stanselmminstitute.org/files/SERMON%20227.pdf>

98 <https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/mediterranean-diet-00884>

99 <https://www.barillacfn.com/en/magazine/food-and-sustainability/the-mediterranean-diet-as-an-example-of-sustainability/>

100 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259498425_Environmental_footprints_of_Mediterranean_versus_Western_dietary_patterns_Beyond_the_health_benefits_of_the_Mediterranean_diet

those with low environmental impacts which contribute to food and nutrition security and to healthy life for present and future generations."¹⁰¹

Jesus essentially ate a Mediterranean diet and lived the Mediterranean Lifestyle, - Dr. Don Colbert¹⁰² reveals us¹⁰³.

'Man shall not live by bread alone, but by every word that proceeds out of the mouth of God.'¹⁰⁴

Saint Ambrose was sure: "let us drink with joy the sober abundance of the Spirit (Laeti bibamussobriam profusionem Spiritus)".¹⁰⁵ The expression *sober abundance* is not just a paradox or a purely poetic theme; it is full of meaning and truth for a man. The effect of abundance is always to make man come out of himself, from his own narrow limit. But while in material abundance a homo sapiens sapiens comes out of himself to live *below* his rational level, almost like beasts - in spiritual abundance, he goes out of himself to live *above* of one's reason, in the very horizon of Consciousness.¹⁰⁶

With our *Golden Hours Idea* we have chosen to attract the everyone's attention to Mediterranean lifestyle and to abandon those who have made us selfish, senseless, proud exploiters. Still now there are those who do not believe in the serious situation and continue senselessly to destroy our common home.

It means to be sincere. "Sincerity is the foundation of the spiritual life",¹⁰⁷- Albert Schweitzer¹⁰⁸ wrote. Ralph Waldo Emerson amazingly described the significance of sincerity in an 1841 essay, *The Over-Soul*.¹⁰⁹

It means non to belong to "the Society of the Spectacle"¹¹⁰

It means to be simple with the simplicity that comes from sobriety. A sobriety that is not misery, but the daily ability to use the means without becoming their servants and slaves.. Using what a man needs for life, but don't letting himself to become its servant.

Tiller said: "You have to be willing to suspend judgment, be open individuals and learn as much as possible about yourself, others the world. With meditation it is possible to push oneself to explore one's inner self ".¹¹¹ Saint Ignatius went further, writing: "Allow me to become food for the wild beasts, through whose instrumentality it will be granted me to attain to God. I am the wheat of God, and let me be ground by the teeth of the wild beasts,

101 <https://www.fao.org/3/i3004e/i3004e00.htm>

102 Dr. Don Colbert graduated from Oral Roberts University Medical School in 1984 and completed his internship and residency at Florida Hospital. Dr. Colbert has been board certified in Family Practice for over 25 years, focusing his practices on anti-aging and integrative medicine in Central Florida. He is also a New York Times "Best Selling Author" for writing over 40 books, like "The Hormone Zone," "Keto Zone Diet" and "Let Food Be Your Medicine."

<https://drcolbert.com/about-us/>

103 <https://www.latimes.com/archives/la-xpm-2003-aug-30-me-reldiet30-story.html>

104 Matthew 4:4, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Matthew_4:4

105 <https://emmanuel.info/en/charis/>

106 On the experience of being drunk see: <https://www.ilcattolico.it/catechesi/spirito-santo/laeti-bibamus-sobriam-profusionem-spiritus.html>

107 Schweitzer Albert, *The Light Within Us*,(2015) 33

108 Ludwig Philipp Albert Schweitzer OM (1875 – 1965) was an Alsatian polymath. He received the 1952 Nobel Peace Prize for his philosophy of "Reverence for Life". He was a theologian, organist, musicologist, writer, humanitarian, philosopher, and physician. A Lutheran, Schweitzer challenged both the secular view of Jesus as depicted by the historical-critical method current at this time, as well as the traditional Christian view.

109 *The Conduct of Life* is a collection of essays by Ralph Waldo Emerson published in 1860 and revised in 1876. In this volume, Emerson sets out to answer "the question of the times:" "How shall I live?" It is composed of nine essays, each preceded by a poem. These nine essays are largely based on lectures Emerson held throughout the country, including for a young, mercantile audience in the lyceums of the Midwestern boomtowns of the 1850s.

The Conduct of Life has been named as both one of Emerson's best works and one of his worst. It was one of Emerson's most successful publications and has been identified as a source of influence for a number of writers, including Friedrich Nietzsche.

110 Debord, Guy. *Society of the Spectacle*. Rebel Press, London, 1992.

111 <https://www.pianetablunews.it/2014/07/30/professore-emerito-william-tiller-siamo-esseri-spirituali-che-abitano-un-bio-corpo/>

that I may be found the pure bread of Christ".¹¹² Jesus said: "Those who eat my flesh and drink my blood have (...) life"¹¹³

Éric-Emmanuel Schmit¹¹⁴ in his *Le sumo qui ne pouvait pas grossir* writes:

"- You don't need the religion to live.

- the religion, maybe not. But the spirituality, yes."

("- On n'a pas besoin de religion pour vivre.

- De religion, peut-être pas. Mais de spiritualité, si.")¹¹⁵

How many precious different thoughts and ideas! At the same time, there are ideals and goals common to all peoples, rooted in the depths of joined human spirit. Therefore, each nation, having achieved the practical expression of its right to independent existence in the field of thought, conscience, religion, language and everyday characteristics, then must adhere to these ideals and strive for these goals, only realizing them in accordance with its natural properties. This is how unity in diversity is achieved, which is the true task of culture.

Following Lautsi case¹¹⁶, we celebrate this year, we call for sharing the idea that all conditions of modern European culture should be Christian.¹¹⁷

Lautsi has become a symbol of the current conflict concerning the future of the cultural and religious identity of Europe. The conflict contains on one side proponents of the complete secularization of Europe, and on the other, those who desire an open Europe, one that is faithful to its identity and historical roots. Confronted with this attempt at a complete de-Christianization of Europe, 20 European countries joined in an unprecedented approach to reaffirm the legitimacy of Christianity in Europe.¹¹⁸

Many readers would listen to Einstein: "being a lover of freedom, when the revolution came in Germany, I looked to the universities to defend it, knowing that they had always boasted of their devotion to the cause of truth; but, no, the universities immediately were silenced. Then I looked to the great editors of the newspapers whose flaming editorials in days gone by had proclaimed their love of freedom; but they, like the universities, were silenced in a few short weeks. [...] Only the Church stood squarely across the path of

112 The Epistle of Ignatius to the Romans, <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/0107.htm>

113 <https://www.biblegateway.com/verse/en/John%206%3A54>

114 Éric-Emmanuel Schmitt (1960) is a Franco-Belgian playwright, short story writer, novelist, as well as a film director, translated into 46 languages and performed in more than 50 countries.

<https://www.eric-emmanuel-schmitt.com/home-official-website.html>;

<https://www.avvenire.it/agora/pagine/schmitt-convertito>

115 *Le Sumo qui ne pouvait pas grossir* of Eric-Emmanuel Schmitt is the fifth part of the Cycle de l'Invisible, published in 2009.

116 On March 18, 2011, the European Court of Human Rights, sitting as a Grand Chamber ("GC"), pronounced its judgment in the case of *Soile Lautsi and Others v. Italy*. (*Lautsi v. Italy*, App. No. 30814/06, 2011 Eur. Ct. H.R. (G.C.)) By this final judgment, which overturned a unanimous judgment rendered on November 3, 2009, by the Second Section of the Strasbourg Court (A Section is an administrative entity, and a Chamber is a judicial formation of the Court within a given Section. The Court has five Sections in which Chambers are formed. Each Section has a President, a Vice-President, and a number of other judges), the Grand Chamber (The Grand Chamber is made up of 17 judges: the Court's President and Vice-Presidents, the Section Presidents, and the national judge, together with other judges selected by drawing of lots. The initiation of proceedings before the Grand Chamber takes two different forms: referral and relinquishment. After a Chamber judgment has been delivered, the parties may request referral of the case to the Grand Chamber and such requests are accepted on an exceptional basis. A panel of judges of the Grand Chamber decides whether or not the case should be referred to the Grand Chamber for fresh consideration. Cases are also sent to the Grand Chamber when relinquished by a Chamber, although this is also exceptional. The Chamber to which a case is assigned can relinquish it to the Grand Chamber if the case raises a serious question affecting the interpretation of the Convention or if there is a risk of inconsistency with a previous judgment of the Court. See *The Court, EUROPEAN COURT OF HUMAN RIGHTS*, (Aug. 4, 2012, 3:18 PM),

<http://www.echr.coe.int/ECHR/EN/Header/The+Court/The+Court/The+Grand+Chamber/>) decided, by fifteen votes to two, that the compulsory display of crucifixes in Italian State-school classrooms did not violate Article 2 of the first Protocol of the European Convention on Human Rights. (*Lautsi*, 2011 Eur. Ct. H.R. §§ 77-78)

117 In this paper we will not touch the 'margin of appreciation' doctrine, secularism and religious freedom which operate on two different levels: the public one and the private one.

118 See in detail: <https://eclj.org/echr-crucifix-case-20-european-countries-support-the-crucifix>

Hitler's campaign for suppressing truth. I never had any special interest in the Church before, but now I feel a great affection and admiration because the Church alone has had the courage and persistence to stand for intellectual truth and moral freedom. I am forced thus to confess that what I once despised I now praise unreservedly."¹¹⁹

The ECtHR indirectly promotes and perpetuates the notion of Christian secularism by describing Christian symbols as compatible with secular values.¹²⁰

Our *Golden Hours Idea* is for supporting the ethic of reverence for life.

The phrase "reverence for life" is taken from the work of Albert Schweitzer. He wrote: "the ethic of Reverence for Life is the ethic of love widened into universality. It is the ethic of Jesus, now recognized as a logical consequence of thought."¹²¹

Schweitzer developed a perspective he called "Reverence for Life," which he used to describe a universal concept of ethics that requires a respect for the lives of all other beings, and by demanding the highest development of our individual skills and aspirations.

Our *Golden Hours Idea* uses Schweitzer's work to outline a philosophy for everyone that includes ethical foundations, relationships between humans and nature. Our idea specifically addresses the business implications of Schweitzer's ethic regarding the development a Human Rights Policy (the "Guiding principles on business and human rights"¹²²)

Many readers would agree with Vl.Solovjev¹²³ that all conditions of modern European culture should be Christian.¹²⁴ This determines what should be the unity of not only ideals and goals, but also of the ways to achieve them.

In a way, the Lautsi case, gave an opportunity for Catholics, Orthodox, and some Protestants, including Evangelicals, to clarify their common idea.

Benedict XVI in his message for the World Day of Peace 2011¹²⁵ explained that, due to the link between religious and moral freedom, "[r]eligious freedom should be understood, then, not merely as immunity from coercion, but even more fundamentally as an ability to order one's own choices in accordance with truth".¹²⁶ In the same way, he said that "[a] freedom which is hostile or indifferent to God becomes self-negating and does not guarantee full

119 This statement was reported in the article Religion: German Martyrs, published in Time Magazine (December 23, 1940).

120 <https://www.eur.nl/en/eshcc/news/giulia-evolvi-publishes-article-about-european-court-human-rights-case-law-religious-symbols>

121 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324208609_On_the_thought_of_Albert_Schweitzer_1875-1965

122 https://www.ohchr.org/documents/publications/guidingprinciplesbusinesshr_en.pdf

123 Vladimir Sergeevich Solovjev (1853 - 1900) is a Russian philosopher, poet, pamphleteer, literary critic; honorary academician of the Imperial Academy of Sciences in the category of fine literature (1900), played a significant role in the development of Russian philosophy and poetry at the end of the 19th century and in the spiritual renaissance of the early -20th century. He stood at the origins of the Russian "spiritual revival" at the beginning of the 20th century, influenced the religious philosophy of Nikolai Berdyaev, Sergei Bulgakov, Sergei and Yevgeny Trubetskoy, Pavel Florensky, Semyon Frank, as well as the work of the Symbolist poets Andrei Bely, Alexander Blok and others. He founded a movement known as Christian philosophy. The philosophical legacy of Vl. Solovjev is a significant page in Russian social thought in the second half of the 19th century. Vl.Solovjev is one of the central figures in Russian philosophy of the 19th century both in his scientific contribution and in the influence he exerted on the views of scientists. Solovjev objected to the division of Christianity into Catholicism and Orthodoxy and defended the ideas of ecumenism. He developed a new approach to the study of man, which became predominant in Russian philosophy and psychology of the late 19th - early 20th centuries. (Yaroshevsky M.G. Ch. VIII. The development of psychology in Russia. 3. University professors. Vl. S. Solovjev: the neo-Christian concept of the soul // History of psychology from antiquity to the middle of the XX century (Russian), M (1996). Solovjev posed many ideological problems that are relevant to this day. The problem of the relationship between culture and politics is among them. The problem of the relationship between culture and politics was solved by Solovjev both in theoretical terms and in connection with the transformation of the socio-political situation in Russia. Consideration of the legacy of Solovjev from this perspective allows a deeper understanding of the various facets of his proposed solution to the problem of the relationship between culture and politics.

124 Koni AF, Vladimir Sergeevich Solovjev, 24 (1873)

125 Pope Benedict XVI, Religious Freedom, the Path to Peace, Message for the World Day of Peace (Jan. 1, 2011).

126 Ibid

respect for others”.¹²⁷ It was the most in-depth declaration on religious freedom. The reminder that freedom is subordinate to truth is fundamental, and it constitutes a noticeable clarification of the present view on this point. Similarly, the message insists on “the public dimension of religion, *and in particular, it warns that “to eclipse the public role of religion is to create a society which is unjust.*”¹²⁸

Even more directly, the representative of the Russian Orthodox Church declared to the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE), referring to the Lautsi case, “I consider the concept of the religious neutrality of a state to be the most disputable issue in the OSCE area. Attempts to establish a model religiously-neutral state in Europe have many negative implications”.¹²⁹

This is not new, in the Encyclical *Mater et Magistra* of 15 May 1961, Pope John XXIII denounced the modern era: “[t]he most perniciously typical aspect of the modern era consists in the absurd attempt to reconstruct a solid and fruitful temporal order divorced from God, who is, in fact, the only foundation on which it can endure”.¹³⁰ Benedict XVI wrote: “whoever does not know God, even though he may have multiple hopes, is hopeless ultimately”.¹³¹

In his *Markings* ex UN Secretary-General Dag Hammarskjöld wrote: “God does not die on the day when we cease to believe in a personal deity, but we die on the day when our lives cease to be illumined by the steady radiance, renewed daily, of a wonder, the source of which is beyond all reason. In this sense we can understand the words of the mystic Saint John of the Cross: What prepares the soul to be united with God is the desire for God.”¹³² Dag Hammarskjöld continued: “The language of religion is a set of formulas that record a basic spiritual experience. Faith is a state of mind and soul.”

And change your mind,
be the Light and
move you in the direction you want
behind thought and reality.
Human consciousness and physical reality
influence each other.
Thoughts can change reality.
Change to learn about yourself, others and the world.
All that we are is the result of what we have thought.
The Light sings the dream of the world:
you become logos made flesh!
May all people contend to have generated the Light ...

We don't need to change the world, we need to have/become Teacher. Einstein turns our attention to Dostojevski: “Dostojevski gives me more than any scientist, more than Gauss!”¹³³

Vito Mancuso¹³⁴ offers the four masters¹³⁵ who together foreshadow an itinerary: Socrates, the educator; Buddha, the physician; Confucius, the politician; Jesus, the prophet. The

127 Ibid

128 Ibid

129 Kipshidze Vakhtang, Address during the Supplementary Human Dimension Meeting on Freedom of Religion or Belief of the OSCE, Vienna (Dec. 9–10, 2010) available at <http://www.mospat.ru/en/2010/12/13/news32334/>

130 <https://cardinalsblog.adw.org/2013/06/03/blessed-pope-john-xxiii-and-the-second-vatican-council/>

131 Benedict XVI from the Encyclical Letter *Spe Salvi*, http://www.vatican.va/content/benedict-xvi/it/encyclicals/documents/hf_ben-xvi_enc_20071130_spe-salvi.html

132 Quoted in <https://catholicstrength.com/tag/the-soul-experiences-substantial-touches-of-union-with-god/>

133 In 1920; quoted in Moszowski Alexander, *Conversation with Einstein*, Horizon Press, New York, 185 (1970).

134 Vito Mancuso (1962) is an Italian theologian and teacher.

135 Mancuso Vito, *The Four Masters* (Italian) (2020)

goal is the most important teacher: the inner teacher, the fifth teacher.¹³⁶ Going back to the ancient spiritual and philosophical traditions of humanity, in the thoughts of these four figures Vito Mancuso identifies the teachings that are still valid and precious for us today. Thus their words become a decisive guide to travel with greater awareness the arduous paths of our existence, to live in the chaos that we experience every day, and to trace a new path.

Our Golden Hours Idea is the mystical idea.

Weil¹³⁷ says: "At the bottom of the heart of every human being, from earliest infancy until the tomb, there is something that goes on indomitably expecting, in the teeth of all experience of crimes committed, suffered, and witnessed, that good and not evil will be done to him. It is this above all that is sacred in every human being".¹³⁸ That's why the mystical experience isn't a privilege of few people, perhaps closed in a convent, but a wealth life, a complete and profound experience, a human characteristic, human excellence, a summit. "The mass of a body is a measure of its energy content",¹³⁹-Einstein said.

Eastern thought is a mystical thought that arises from the awareness of the unity and interdependence of all phenomena, so many moments can be mystical, you just need to feel part of this integrated system. Eastern mystics have a direct experience of reality and come to the enlightenment which is precisely an *absolute knowledge*, intuitive, direct, undivided, it is an embrace.

Dag Hammarskjöld wrote in his *Markings* that the explanation of how man should live a life of active service to society in complete harmony with himself as an active member of the community of the spirit, he found in the writings of those great medieval mystics for whom *submission* was the way of self-realization. In the *honesty of the mind* and in the *interiority* they found the strength to say yes to every request that the needs of their neighbor put before them, and to say yes to any fate life had in store for them. For them Love - this word so abused and misunderstood - simply meant a surplus of strength, entirely filled them, when they began to live in self-forgetfulness. And this love found natural expression in an unhesitating fulfillment of duty and an unreserved acceptance of life, whatever it brought them personally: fatigue, suffering, or happiness. We share the Dag Hammarskjöld's view that their discoveries on the laws of inner life and action have not lost their meaning.¹⁴⁰

John O'Donohue supports us in *Anam Cara (friendly soul in Gaelic)*.¹⁴¹ When St Patrick arrived in Ireland in the 5th century AD, he found Celtic people and a vivid spiritual tradition, thousands of years old. The Celts had a refined and passionate sense of the divine; their imagery gave birth to an inner friendship that held nature, divinity, the underworld and the human world in one embrace. The Celts did not separate the visible from the invisible, time from eternity, the human from the divine. The ancient wisdom, poetry and grace of Celtic spirituality awaken and enrich the beauty the landscape of our heart. O'Donohue opens us the magical and discreet world of the divine that is in us, that place of the soul where there is no distance between us and the eternal. We explore themes such as the mystery of natural rights and freedoms, common good, the spirituality of the senses, work as a poetic of growth, old age as the art of an inner harvest, and death

136 <https://www.vitomancuso.it/libri/i-quattro-maestri/>

137 Simone Adolphine Weil (1909-1943) was a French philosopher, mystic and writer, whose fame is linked, in addition to the vast essay-literary production, to the dramatic existential events that she went through, from the choice to leave teaching to experience the working condition, up to her commitment as a partisan activist, despite persistent health problems.

138 Weil Simone, *An Anthology*, 51 (2000)

139 Einstein A, *Does the inertia of a body depend upon its energy content?* (September 27, 1905)

140 More details: Hoskins R. Taylor, *Dag Hammarskjöld: The Diplomat, The Mystic, The Man, The Mystery* Hardcover (2014)

141 O'Donohue John, *Anam Cara* (1998)

as the ultimate homecoming. Surviving to the present day, Celtic respect for the soul is a vibrant spiritual legacy unique in the Western world.

“The twenty-first century will be religious, or it will not be (Le vingt-et-unième siècle sera religieux, o¹⁴² il ne sera pas)”.¹⁴³ This prophetic word of André Malraux¹⁴⁴ is often quoted. In the Age of Pisces,¹⁴⁵ leaders were those with material resources. But they didn't have Spirits.

We need prophets. The prophets are those who see, further away, before and in events, but they see and that seeing is also a feeling, feeling something that speaks inside them. And then the prophets - and we can all be prophets - are true antennas and true megaphones in humanity, points on which to rest for the light that must enlighten and guide us. The evolutionary development of our species continues only if there is love towards life, which means openness and harmonious relationships.

“The harvest is abundant but the laborers are few”,¹⁴⁶ - Jesus Christ said.

The rights of human being are abundant. We need great mystics who become great politicians\lawmakers\judges. The mystic that one day develops in politician is a proof that he is genuine: some great mystics have become great politicians. But they remained mystics.

We pay special attention to the UN's secretary-general Dag Hammarskjöld, whose spiritual set of beliefs influenced his political activity. He was searching for universality and solidarity, just as it is written down in the charter of the UN. While in office, Hammarskjöld was able to unite personal belief and political ratio. This is the main reason why he became a respected and true international civil servant. Hammarskjöld was neither a pure idealist nor a pure realist. The legacy of Hammarskjöld unites mystics and realistic political engagement. In doing so it draws on the lessons learned from a “practical mystical” and international civil servant.

His life and his death, his words and his action, have done more to shape public expectations of the office, and indeed of the Organisation, than those of any other man or woman in its history.

His wisdom and his modesty, his unimpeachable integrity and single-minded devotion to duty, have set a standard for all servants of the international community — and especially, of course for his successors — which is simply impossible to live up to. There can be no better rule of thumb for a lawyer/politician/judge etc, as he/she approaches each new challenge or crisis, than to ask himself/herself, “how would Hammarskjöld have handled this?”

“I realise now that in comparison to him, I am a small man. He was the greatest statesman of our century,”¹⁴⁷ - John F. Kennedy said.

In his Markings Dag Hammarskjöld proposes: “no life gave greater satisfaction than a life of selfless service to one's country and humanity. This service required the sacrifice of all private interests, but at the same time the courage to stand firm for one's convictions, accepting as troubles so happiness.” Dag Hammarskjöld had the conviction¹⁴⁸ that, “in the

142 <https://www.helloastrology.com/pisces/age-of-pisces/>

143 <https://www.lesoir.be/art/1136269/article/soirmag/soirmag-histoire/2016-02-29/xxie-siecle-sera-religieux-ou-ne-sera-pas>

144 Georges André Malraux (1901–1976) was a French novelist, art theorist, and Minister of Cultural Affairs. Malraux's novel *La Condition Humaine* (Man's Fate) (1933) won the Prix Goncourt. He was appointed by President Charles de Gaulle as Minister of Information (1945–46) and subsequently as France's first Minister of Cultural Affairs during de Gaulle's presidency (1959–1969).

145 <https://www.helloastrology.com/pisces/age-of-pisces/>

146 Luke 10, 1-9

147 John F. Kennedy, during a meeting with an associate of Hammarskjöld, quoted in <https://revistademediacion.com/en/articulos/dag-hammarskjold-apostol-la-mediacion/>

148 Simone Weil had the same conviction. See Weil Simone, *An Anthology*, 51 (2000)

true sense of the Gospel, all men are equal as children of God and must be approached and treated by us as our lords in God”¹⁴⁹.

The true mystics are significant¹⁵⁰

Regarding three Catholics, three frontier men¹⁵¹ Maria Chiara Malaguti¹⁵² said:.. “The canonization process does not only concern Schuman, but also De Gasperi.. People who have dedicated their commitment to the common good ..deserve to be canonized. It is a rare thing and it is a pity that it is so rare, because it is significant.”¹⁵³

The true mystic is who constantly renews his mystical life in the political field.

“Today it is still possible to think of a saintly politician”, -Malaguti says. Indeed we would need even more this type of saints as points of reference. A saintly politician would also be an easier message for us who live our daily life, with all its difficulties .

This is the first revolution that humanity needs today: contemplative human beings (lawyers, judges, politicians). “Contemplation is the highest expression of man’s intellectual and spiritual life...It is spiritual wonder. It is spontaneous awe at the sacredness of life, of being. It is a vivid realization of the fact that life and being in us proceed from an invisible, transcendent and infinitely abundant source. Contemplation is, above all, awareness of the reality of that source”,¹⁵⁴- Merton says.

Perhaps Ivan Ilyin¹⁵⁵’s greatest gift to us, through his writings, is his insight on contemplative living in a world filled with chaos and distraction.¹⁵⁶ He wrote extensively on this subject, in books such as *Singing Heart*.¹⁵⁷ It is consideration of the sacred nature of life. And this life comes from an invisible Source, the divine, transcendent and infinitely rich Spirit. Contemplation makes us aware of the reality of this Source. Contemplation is a spiritual vision that completes. And it can be reached through various ways.

We need human beings (lawyers, judges, politicians etc) of mystical experience, for whom mystical experience is action and action is mystical experience.

“The most important thing is that they (mystics) claim to be able to grasp the ultimate reality in a single experience, in contrast to the long and tortuous deductive sequences of the logical-scientific method of investigation”,¹⁵⁸- Paul Davies¹⁵⁹ said.

149 See in details Bouman Monica, The Quest for Maturity, *Philosophia Reformata*, Vol. 81, No. 1, 32-49 (May 2016), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26547895>

150 <https://www.cittanuova.it/bisogno-politici-santi/?ms=005&se=020>

151 Three Catholics, three frontier men, three persecuted by the Nazi-fascist dictatorships: the French Robert Schuman, the German Konrad Adenauer, the Italian Alcide De Gasperi are the founding fathers of the European Union, Nobel Peace Prize 2012.

152 MARIA CHIARA MALAGUTI, ORDINARY PROFESSOR, Department of Private and Public Economic Law, FACULTY OF ECONOMICS, INTERNATIONAL LAW, Catholic University of the Sacred Heart, Italy

153 <https://www.cittanuova.it/bisogno-politici-santi/?ms=005&se=020>

154 Merton Thomas, *New Seeds of Contemplation* (2003)

155 Ivan Alexandrovich Ilyin (1883–1954) is Russian philosopher and legal scholar. Although forbidden under the Soviet regime, Ilyin’s thoughts and works have come to be more and more appreciated over the last twenty years, especially since his earthly remains were re-interred in Russia in 2005. It is possible to say that he is the favourite Russian thinker of our times. Like all prophets, however, he was of course mainly ignored, unappreciated and even persecuted in his own times. Today, Ilyin is understood to be the voice of the faithful Russian emigration, a spiritual leader, a teacher, a prophet, a visionary preacher. His prophetic insights have been justified since the fall of Communism and the huge interest in his works there now. Ilyin, who died over half a century ago, is the prophet of the new Russia which is being born and which alone can give the contemporary world a viable future, providing that it is given time to grow to fruition in contemporary Russia. One of the problems he worked on was the question: what has eventually led Russia to the tragedy of the revolution?

156 <https://thesaker.is/ivan-ilyin-on-contemplative-love/>

157 Ilyin Ivan, *The Singing Heart: A Book of Quiet Reflections* (2016)

158 Davies Paul, *The Mind of God: The Scientific Basis for a Rational World* (1993). See more on *The Mind of God: Slezak Peter, The mind of god: Science and the search for ultimate meaning*, *Science & Education*, 5(2), 201-212 (January 1996)

159 Paul Charles William Davies (1946) is a British theoretical physicist, cosmologist, astrobiologist, writer and popularizer of science. Regent Professor at the University of Arizona and co-director of its research center "Beyond" (Center for Fundamental Concepts in Science), Principal Investigator of the Center for the Convergence of Physical Sciences and Cancer Biology at the same university, Fellow of the Royal Society of Literature (1999). Templeton Prize

Mystical experience is the Life in a complete, wellness and full way. It's natural access of the most precious human dynamics. It's the anthropological dimension, which belongs to the human being as such. The mystic is the authentic man, the man who lives his humanity as something more (and not less) than pure rationality. It is joyful because mystics feel an integral part of life, of beauty, of its superabundance, of its excess, of its being terribly beautiful, which they experience directly. And it is an experience that cannot be described, it must only be felt. "There are only two ways to live your life. One is as though nothing is a miracle. The other is as though everything is",¹⁶⁰-Einstein said. "God always grants, but not our requests, rather, His promises"¹⁶¹, -D.Bonhoeffer¹⁶² was sure. Jesus Christ promised us some things:" I came so that you may have life and have it abundantly, I will not leave you orphans, I will be with you every day until the end of time, the Father knows what you need.."¹⁶³ *And he is faithful that promised.*¹⁶⁴

The passage to the Age of Aquarius¹⁶⁵ is the promise. It implies the passage to a spiritual person. Spiritual people are leaders the world needs right now. And they must be able to manage all resources: a resource of energy, but also the material resources. Following the words of Isaiah, they "are my witnesses. Is there any God besides me? No, there is no other Rock; I know not one".¹⁶⁶ Spirit is All that is One in the cosmic hologram and all is alchemy, all, created from nothing. And we (lawyers, judges, politicians etc) have access to this technology.

For us, lawyers, judges, politicians etc, it is not enough to wake up every morning, we need to have Spirit, we need to be aware that everything is given to us, delivered as a gift, and that only if we know how to *keep and cultivate*, it will bear fruit.¹⁶⁷

This is chiefly done by using the Italian School approach of international relations theory¹⁶⁸ while at same time pointing out the impact of positive mimesis.¹⁶⁹

Our Golden Hours Idea is to adopt mimetic theory, to make more and more widespread the notion of positive, loving, creative, and nonviolent mimesis.

Girard¹⁷⁰ himself used the term "mimesis" (derived from the Greek) rather than "imitation" partly to disambiguate it from mere imitation.¹⁷¹ Mimesis is something that is usually, but not always, hidden. We invite to use a positive form of imitation—for instance, the imitation of virtuous people.

The philosopher Baruch Spinoza, who never writes specifically about mimetic desire and seemed to have more of an individualist version of desire than Girard,¹⁷² nevertheless

Winner (1995).

160 Quoted by Gilbert Fowler White in *Journal of France and Germany (1942–1944)*; quoted in Robert E. Hinshaw, *Living with Nature's Extremes: The Life of Gilbert Fowler White*, Big Earth Publishing, 62 (2006). Gilbert Fowler White quoted this sentence without however specifying the occasion in which Einstein would have uttered it.

161 Quoted in <https://donboscosalesianportal.org/pray-always/>

162 Dietrich Bonhoeffer (1906–1945) was a Lutheran pastor, theologian, anti-Nazi dissident, and key founding member of the Confessing Church. His writings on Christianity's role in the secular world have become widely influential, and his book *The Cost of Discipleship* has been described as a modern classic.

163 *I came that they may have life, and have it abundantly* (Jn 10:10); *Your Father knows what you need before you ask him* (Matthew 6:8)

164 Hebrews 10:19-25

165 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Age_of_Aquarius; <https://www.elle.com/uk/life-and-culture/culture/longform/a33093/astrologers-explain-age-of-aquarius/>

166 Isaiah, 44.8

167 Yes, God wants us to bear fruit. ... Galatians 5:22-23 describes the fruit produced in us by the Spirit Christ gives us.

168 Calcara Antonio, Vittori Davide, *Italians do it better? The Italian approach to the international relations*, March 2019, *European Political Science* 18(2):1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41304-019-00207-3>

169 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mimetic_theory

170 René Noël Théophile Girard (1923 – 2015) was a French polymath, historian, literary critic, and philosopher of social science. Girard was the author of nearly thirty books, with his writings spanning many academic domains.

171 <https://mimetictheory.com/who-is-rene-girard/>

172 <https://alexanderdouglass.medium.com/spinoza-and-mimetic-desire-f4ef0b0bde1d>

refers to “emulation” —“the desire for a thing which is generated in us from the fact that we imagine others like us to have the same desire”.¹⁷³

Notre Dame professor Ann W. Astell has a commentary on something that could be called positive mimesis with her essay “Saintly Mimesis, Contagion, and Empathy in the Thought of René Girard, Edith Stein, and Simone Weil.”¹⁷⁴

These laws and this system are the consequences of a fundamental reality grasped by the novelists, which Girard called mimetic desire, “the mimetic character of desire.” This is the content of his first book, *Deceit, Desire and the Novel* (1961).

Mimetic desire, meaning the openness of the human person to what is human and to what is divine, has its theological counterpart in the capacity for transcendence that is given to the human person as creational grace. Thus, it is intrinsically good. However, since God is not directly accessible to humans, mimetic desire can easily be perverted.

And in order to get to positive mimesis one has to go beyond these levels, as a quotation from *I See Satan Fall like Lightning* indicates: “To break the power of [violent] mimetic unanimity, we must postulate a power superior to violent contagion. If we have learned one thing in this study, it is that none exists on earth.”¹⁷⁵

In general, positive imitation, or positive mimesis, is thought to involve decrease envy, rivalry, and resentment.

Any human right isn’t based on the neutrality of a state, but it’s based on the essence of a human being and must be ensured by the state. The degree of realization of this right is precisely something that entirely depends on internal conditions, on the degree of the achieved consciousness (mindfulness). As history has shown atrociously, it is not enough to call oneself a good politician\lawyer\judge\man to be one truly, and not even Christian, and not even Jews, and not even Muslims.

Andrea Emo has shown brightly that what exists in every positive is primarily its original negation, and that therefore otherness is not a goal to be achieved for the existing, but the only place from which it is possible to truly establish his true identity.¹⁷⁶

Is it possible that you don't understand? It is like in Eduardo's old comedy *Natale in casa Cupiello*¹⁷⁷ in which the pretended naive son said and repeated stubbornly: I don't like *il presepio* (Italian nativity scene's character). It is not that he denied *il presepio*, it's that there was the hidden face of the tragedy behind the beautiful *presepio*.

We don't need to change the world, we need to accept the complexity. The German chancellor, Angela Merkel said the idea of people from different cultural backgrounds living happily *side by side* did not work. She claimed the country's attempts to create a multicultural society have *utterly failed*. “This [multicultural] approach has failed, utterly failed”, - Merkel told at the meeting in Potsdam, west of Berlin, in 2010.¹⁷⁸

Does it mean that in Western countries *the complexity* is already announced un looser by politics and by judiciary as a consequence?

Gérard de Nerval¹⁷⁹ helps us to answer: “Free thinker! Do you think you are the only thinker on this earth in which life blazes inside all things? Your liberty does what it wishes with the powers it controls, but when you gather to plan, the universe is not there”.¹⁸⁰

173 Ethics, Part 3, Proposition 27, Scholium

174 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/42943639?seq=1>

175 Girard R, *I See Satan Fall Like Lightning*, 189. <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/235228/pdf>

176 <http://www.bietti.it/negoziola-meraviglia-del-nulla-vita-e-filosofia-di-andrea-emo/>

177 It's a tragicomic play written by Eduardo De Filippo in 1931. It is one of the most appreciated by the public and by critics.

178 <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2010/oct/17/angela-merkel-german-multiculturalism-failed>

179 Gérard Labrunie, known as Gérard de Nerval (1808-1855) is a French writer and poet. He is a major figure in French romanticism, he is best known for his poems and short stories, including his book *Les Filles du feu*, a collection of short stories (the most famous being *Sylvie*), his collection of sonnets (*Les Chimères*) published in 1854 and his new poetic *Aurélia* published in 1855.

180 Gérard de Nerval, *Golden Lines* (translator Robert Bly) (1854), <http://poemhunter.blogspot.com/2007/12/golden-lines.html>

People have made the sin of division from the miracle of uniqueness. The globalization as well as the present disintegration of societies, witnessed especially in Western countries that intensifies the crisis of collective identities, put a brake on the individualist liberalism that supports the modern concept of human rights and freedoms. From this perspective, the plea of the Italian government in Lautsi in favor of the crucifix as a fundamental symbol of the civilization reveals all its value. Italy, while resolutely desiring to respect individual liberties, refused to renounce to one of its main traditional symbol in the name of the postmodern cultural relativism and nihilism. Italian Ambassador Sergio Busetto expressed it as follows: “respecting the religious identity of an individual must be possible while respecting the religious identity of the society in which he lives”.¹⁸¹

The interventions of twenty-one Member States to support Italy in Lautsi v Italy case demonstrate that the postmodern model of liberal democracy, cut off from its cultural and religious roots, has not entirely conquered Europe. It may even be drawing back, due to the social and cultural constraints imposed by globalization. Z.Bauman is sure:

“Globalization is the last failed hope that, somewhere, there still exists a land where one can escape and find happiness. Or the last failed hope that, somewhere, there still exists a land different from yours in terms of being able to oppose the sense of meaninglessness, the loss of criteria and, ultimately, moral blindness and the loss of sensitivity”.¹⁸²

“Be the change you wish to see in the world.” Most of us have heard this quote, attributed to Mohandas Gandhi, Arleen Lorraine, Ernest Troutner, Diane Kennedy Pike, or to Anonymous¹⁸³ and perhaps even been inspired by it. It’s a beautiful sentiment and one that reminds us how everyone has the power to make an impact.

But when we hear about so many global issues on the news, it can be difficult to believe that just one person can make a difference.

Luckily, social change doesn’t have to happen instantly or on your own. By working together to change lives one day at a time, our joined actions can have a meaningful impact.

Our *Golden Hours Idea* is for making the difference. What difference do you want to make?

Change is not just bottom up or top down. It’s both. Without the boy’s small act, there is no inspiration to change. Without the involvement of institutions, systems, processes, there is no sustainable change at scale.

Let us mention “the starfish story” to you as a metaphor for organizational change, and you our readers instantly know what we mean.

The story has spread widely, and you’ve probably come across it yourself.

The original version is a 16-page essay titled “The Star Thrower,” written by Loren Eiseley and published in 1969.¹⁸⁴

Most people, though, are familiar with a short adaptation like this one:

One day, an old man was walking along a beach that was littered with thousands of starfish that had been washed ashore by the high tide. As he walked he came upon a young boy who was eagerly throwing the starfish back into the ocean, one by one.

Puzzled, the man looked at the boy and asked what he was doing. Without looking up from his task, the boy simply replied, “I’m saving these starfish, Sir”.

The old man chuckled aloud, “Son, there are thousands of starfish and only one of you. What difference can you make?”

The boy picked up a starfish, gently tossed it into the water and turning to the man, said, “I made a difference to that one!”

181 Busetto Sergio, Ambassador of Italy, Opening speech of the symposium organised by the ECLJ, the CNR and the Italian Embassy, at the Council of Europe (Apr. 30 2010) available at

https://classic.iclrs.org/content/blurp/files/ARTICLE_LAUTSI_PUPPINCK_English_BYU_Law_Review.pdf

182 Bauman Zygmunt, *Moral Blindness: The Loss of Sensitivity in Liquid Modernity* (2013)

183 <https://quoteinvestigator.com/2017/10/23/be-change/>

184 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Star_Thrower

If you want to make a difference, you can start right where you are. And with persistence, passion, and some luck, you can inspire and connect others, enabling new possibilities to emerge. You can create the chance to accomplish something together that no one person would or could have done on their own.

Carlo Molari¹⁸⁵ said that “the universe is a system composed of other systems. They are complex, they continually adapt to their surroundings. We too are part of this constantly changing system of relationships”.¹⁸⁶ Molari speaks of the *opportunities of time*, which must be seized with an open and available attitude, like an open door, in order to be able to welcome the elements that are most suitable for us.

We human beings need to feel like citizens of the cosmos. It is the highest feeling, the one that generates a great force inside and towards the environment that surrounds us, a great force of intense participation in the motion of life in which we are placed.

Feeling such participation helps us to establish harmonious relationships, the adaptation of the inside with the outside, helps us to connect with others who are also part of the universe. It is a vision that gives security, that makes us feel solid, on a broad foundation.

Teilhard de Chardin named this feeling an awakening towards ever wider forms of humanity.¹⁸⁷ S. Weil claimed that union with the entire universe causes a kind of symbiosis.¹⁸⁸ Psychologist Otto Rank¹⁸⁹ sees mental health in this.¹⁹⁰

Eastern spirituality has always supported the positivity of such mental orientation.¹⁹¹

For Pema Chödrön¹⁹² the eight worldly dharmas¹⁹³ can become the means to let's become wiser, kinder and more satisfied.¹⁹⁴

This stems from the belief that a creative energy acts in the cosmos that needs to be welcomed in us to create new forms, never developed. This is why a man is a co-creator, in fact the evolutionary process has been transferred to a man, in each of human beings. Then in this vision our action appears in our limit and at the same time in our task, which is exactly that of facilitating, helping, supporting the actions of everyone, of the entire community, so that the peculiarities of each one develop in a harmonious way. “For all that has been, Thanks. To all that shall be, Yes”.¹⁹⁵ Dag Hammarskjöld testified: “I don't know Who, or what, put the question, I don't know when it was put. I don't even remember answering. But at some moment I did answer Yes to Someone, or Something, and from

185 Carlo Molari (1928) is an Italian presbyter and theologian.

http://www.rocce.cittadella.org/rocce/autori/00000112_Molari.html

186 Molari Carlo, *The spiritual journey of the Christian*.

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187 See in detail: King Ursula, *Teilhard de Chardin's vision of science, religion and planetary humanity: A challenge to the contemporary world*, *Journal for the Study of Religion*, vol.31 no.1 Pretoria (2018),

http://www.scielo.org.za/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1011-76012018000100009&lng=pt&nrm=iso&tlng=pt

188 See in detail: Lowtoo Bharatee, *Love for God's Necessity: the ambiguity of Simone Weil's hupomone* (2009),

<http://arno.uvt.nl/show.cgi?fid=96578>

189 Otto Rank (1884–1939) was an Austrian psychoanalyst, writer, and teacher. Born in Vienna, he was one of Sigmund Freud's closest colleagues for 20 years, a prolific writer on psychoanalytic themes, editor of the two leading analytic journals of the era, managing director of Freud's publishing house, and a creative theorist and therapist. In 1926, Rank left Vienna for Paris and, for the remainder of his life, led a successful career as a lecturer, writer, and therapist in France and the United States.

190 See in detail: Hecht Philip J, *The "Fine Line" of Otto Rank* (1994),

<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/231833667.pdf>

191 See *ex gratia*: King Ursula, *Towards a New Mysticism: Teilhard De Chardin and Eastern Religions Hardcover* (1980)

192 Pema Chödrön (born Deirdre Blomfield-Brown, 1936) is an American Tibetan Buddhist. She is an ordained nun, former acharya of Shambhala Buddhism and disciple of Chögyam Trungpa Rinpoche. Chödrön has written several dozen books and audiobooks, and is principal teacher at Gampo Abbey in Nova Scotia, Canada.

193 On eight worldly concerns see: https://encyclopediaofbuddhism.org/wiki/Eight_worldly_concerns

194 <https://pemachodronfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/The-Essential-Pema-Study-Guide.pdf>

195 Hammarskjöld Dag, *Markings* (1963)

that hour I was certain that existence is meaningful and that, therefore, my life, in self-surrender, had a goal”¹⁹⁶

“Life has to have the meaning”,¹⁹⁷ - says Tiller.

Great V. Frankl¹⁹⁸ said *quasi* the same thing in his logotherapy. In his book Frankl quotes Nietzsche's words: “Those who have a 'why' to live, can bear with almost any 'how'”¹⁹⁹

“You are here in order to enable the world to live more amply, with greater vision, with a finer spirit of hope and achievement. You are here to enrich the world, and you impoverish yourself if you forget the errand.”²⁰⁰—Woodrow Wilson²⁰¹ sustains us.

We don't need to change the world, we need to lay the foundations for a "philosophy of Integral ecology". Integral ecology is a key concept in Pope Francis' encyclical on ecology.²⁰² In seeking solutions to the complex environmental crisis, Pope Francis calls for an integrated approach that explains interrelatedness in the cosmic reality.

Our Golden Hours Idea is to suggest a revision and combination of the insights of Pierre Teilhard de Chardin²⁰³ and Alfred North Whitehead²⁰⁴ for a balance between multiplicity and unity, between multiple subjects of experience and the higher-order levels of existence and activity, which they achieve by their dynamic interaction.

We need the philosophy, capable of problematizing the very notion of "ecosystem"²⁰⁵, understood, according to what Giorgio Parisi²⁰⁶ and Carlo Rovelli and others have already said, as a complex network of inextricable relationships, and a peculiar object of quantum

196 <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/829100-i-don-t-know-who-or-what-put-the>

197 <https://excellencereporter.com/2015/03/20/dr-william-a-tiller-working-hypotheses-regarding-the-meaning-of-life/>

198 Viktor Emil Frankl (1905 – 1997) was an Austrian Holocaust survivor, neurologist, psychiatrist, philosopher and author. (Frankl Viktor, *Recollections: An Autobiography* (2008); Klingberg Haddon, *When Life Calls Out to Us: The Love and Lifework of Viktor and Elly Frankl* (2001)). He was the founder of logotherapy based on the premise that the primary motivational force of an individual is to find a meaning in life. It is a meaning-centered school of psychotherapy, considered the Third Viennese School of Psychotherapy (Länge Alfred, *From Viktor Frankl's Logotherapy to Existential Analytic psychotherapy*; in: *European Psychotherapy 2014/2015*. Austria: Home of the World's Psychotherapy. Serge Sulz, Stefan Hagspiel (Eds.). p. 67. (2015)), following Freud's psychoanalysis and Adler's individual psychology. Logotherapy is part of existential and humanistic psychology theories. (Redsand Anna, *Viktor Frankl: A Life Worth Living*, Houghton Mifflin Harcourt (2006)).

Frankl is the author of over 39 books; he is most noted for his best-selling book *Man's Search for Meaning* based on his experiences in various Nazi concentration camps. (Schatzmann Morton, *Obituary: Viktor Frankl*. *The Independent* (UK) (5 September 1997), <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/people/obituary-viktor-frankl-1237506.html>)

199 Frankl Viktor E (1946), *Man's Search for Meaning*, (1997).

200 <https://www.barrywehmiller.com/post/blog/2020/11/19/wise-words-to-change-the-world>

201 Thomas Woodrow Wilson (1856 – 1924) was an American politician and academic who served as the 28th president of the United States from 1913 to 1921. A member of the Democratic Party, Wilson served as the president of Princeton University and as the governor of New Jersey before winning the 1912 presidential election. As President, Wilson changed the nation's economic policies and led the United States into World War I in 1917. He was the leading architect of the League of Nations, and his progressive stance on foreign policy came to be known as Wilsonianism.

202 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Laudato_si%27

203 Pierre Teilhard de Chardin, S.J. (1881 – 1955), was a French Jesuit priest and scientist, professor of geology at the Catholic Institute in Paris, director of the National Geologic Survey of China, and director of the National Research Center of France. He charted a new path in reconciling Christian theology with evolutionary science. Teilhard de Chardin was a prophet, a great intuitive, a mind open to the spirit (*grace*, say the clergymen), an excellent intelligence who knew how to look from above and had a multimedia vision of things which is the evolutionary vision.

204 Alfred North Whitehead OM FRS FBA (1861 – 1947) was an English mathematician and philosopher. He is best known as the defining figure of the philosophical school known as process philosophy, which today has found application to a wide variety of disciplines, including ecology, theology, education, physics, biology, economics, and psychology, among other areas.

205 <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/business-ecosystem.asp>

206 Giorgio Parisi (born 1948) is an Italian theoretical physicist, whose research has focused on quantum field theory, statistical mechanics and complex systems. His best known contributions are the QCD evolution equations for parton densities, obtained with Guido Altarelli, known as the Altarelli–Parisi or DGLAP equations, the exact solution of the Sherrington–Kirkpatrick model of spin glasses, the Kardar–Parisi–Zhang equation describing dynamic scaling of growing interfaces, and the study of whirling flocks of birds. He was awarded the 2021 Nobel Prize in Physics jointly with Klaus Hasselmann and Syukuro Manabe for groundbreaking contributions to theory of complex systems.

mechanics, that proved that interactions between entities, not entities in themselves, are fundamental to reality. It undermines “naive realism,” the notion that science discovers a reality that exists independently of our observation of it. It proposes a so-called “relational” interpretation of quantum mechanics, which says things only exist in relation to other things.

“I alone cannot change the world, but I can cast a stone across the water to create many ripples”²⁰⁷, - these are the words of Mother Teresa.

With our *Golden Hours Idea* we develop policies of inclusion that are more than ever necessary to promote a harmonious life both in front of the request for help of many needy people and with respect to future generations to whom we have moral and ethical duties. We call for collaborations in this direction, based on the most current data in genomics, that should consist in being awake and mindful that we all and everyone of us share one Earth, that “the other” is a part of us and he must be recognized as such.

Only compassionate people would do these things. We invite compassionate people, because following Antonio Gramsci²⁰⁸ we hate the indifferent: “I hate the indifferent. I believe that living means taking sides. Those who really live cannot help being a citizen and a partisan. Indifference and apathy are parasitism, perversion, not life. That is why I hate the indifferent...”²⁰⁹

Our *Golden Hours Idea* is to show how mindful, intelligent businesses must help to protect human rights and nature/ecology, to shape the conditions of mutual trust that are essential to producing future biodiversities we cannot yet imagine.

Insisting that human rights, humans’ economic life are inextricably embedded in nature, we show that our survival will depend on our collective willingness to manage complex natural biodiversity portfolios, a strategy in which contemplating, observing Nature, learning from her are the most important investments we can make.

We call everyone for a radical change in everyday business/personal life to remember that we all are interconnected and are part of relationships with those who preceded us and with those who will come after us to live on planet Earth, of the relationships that are not only direct and horizontal but even more bushy and vertical in time.

Let us close this paper with Saint-Exupéry's prayer:

“Lord, I’m not praying for miracles and visions, I’m only asking for strength for my days. Teach me the art of small steps.

Make me clever and resourceful, so that I can find important discoveries and experiences among the diversity of days.

Help me use my time better. Present me with the sense to be able to judge whether something is important or not.

I pray for the power of discipline and moderation, not only to run throughout my life, but also to live my days reasonably, and observe unexpected pleasures and heights.

207 <https://www.amazon.com/cannot-change-across-ripples-Mother/dp/B084QLCYKJ#:~:text=Enhance%20your%20purchase-,I%20alone%20cannot%20change%20the%20world%2C%20but%20I%20can%20cast,create%20many%20ripples%20%2DMother%20Teresa.>

208 Antonio Francesco Gramsci (1891 – 1937) was an Italian Marxist philosopher, journalist, linguist, writer, and politician. He wrote on philosophy, political theory, sociology, history, and linguistics. He was a founding member and one-time leader of the Communist Party of Italy and was imprisoned by Benito Mussolini's Fascist regime. Gramsci wrote more than 30 notebooks and 3,000 pages of history and analysis during his imprisonment. His *Prison Notebooks* are considered a highly original contribution to 20th-century political theory. Gramsci drew insights from varying sources – not only other Marxists but also thinkers such as Niccolò Machiavelli, Vilfredo Pareto, Georges Sorel, and Benedetto Croce. The notebooks cover a wide range of topics, including Italian history and nationalism, the French Revolution, fascism, Taylorism and Fordism, civil society, folklore, religion and high and popular culture.

209 <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/849434-i-hate-the-indifferent-i-believe-that-living-means-taking>

Save me from the naive belief that everything in life has to go smoothly. Give me the sober recognition that difficulties, failures, fiascos, and setbacks are given to us by life itself to make us grow and mature.

Send me the right person at the right moment, who will have enough courage and love to utter the truth!

I know that many problems solve themselves, so please teach me patience.

You know how much we need friendship. Make me worthy of this nicest, hardest, riskiest and most fragile gift of life.

Give me enough imagination to be able to share with someone a little bit of warmth, in the right place, at the right time, with words or with silence.

Spare me the fear of missing out on life.

Do not give me the things I desire, but the things I need.

Teach me the art of small steps!"²¹⁰

Every bit of warming matters and therefore every action matters. Discussions after COP26, either formally or informally, may push further changes. You are welcome!

210 <https://shanglaurizo.wordpress.com/2016/05/12/a-soulful-prayer-by-antoine-de-saint-exupery/>